

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Innovative fertilizers with added plant extracts in the cultivation of *Valeriana officinalis* and *Raphanus sativus* and in the control of *Botrytis* and powdery mildew

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GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2024, 27(02), 127–136

Publication history: Received on 27 March 2024; revised on 04 May 2024; accepted on 07 May 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscbps.2024.27.2.0172>

Abstract

Research objective: The main objective of this article is to report the results obtained from the use of innovative fertilisers with added plant extracts in agriculture. In particular, this article will deal with two important topics: i) study of the effect of innovative fertilisers on the biomass of vegetable plants; ii) possible control on mortality due to diseases such as *Botrytis* and powdery mildew. The information reported in this research work can support the design of cultivation systems in which agricultural sustainability is fundamental due to the presence of plant extracts as an alternative to synthetic plant protection products.

Materials and Methods: The plants were grown in pots under controlled conditions; 30 seedlings per thesis, divided into 3 replications of 10 plants each, were planted in early January 2024. The plants used in the trial were *Valeriana officinalis* L. and *Raphanus sativus*. The five experimental groups in cultivation were: i) group control, irrigated with water and previously fertilised substrate; ii) group with Aktigen, irrigated with water and previously fertilised substrate, (3 ml per plant once a week); iii) group with Lifegen, irrigated with water and previously fertilised substrate, (3 ml per plant once a week); iv) group with Qi-gen, irrigated with water and previously fertilised substrate, (3 ml per plant once a week); v) Group with *Ecklonia maxima* (EK): (peat 70% + pumice 20%), irrigated with water and previously fertilised substrate, (3 ml per plant once a week). On 5 May 2024, plant height, number of leaves, primary root length (mm), biomass of the aerial and root system, and number of dead plants (*Botrytis* and powdery mildew) were recorded.

Results and Discussion: The experiment showed that the use of innovative fertilisers enriched with plant extracts can indeed significantly improve the vegetative and root growth of *Valeriana officinalis* L. and *Raphanus sativus*. All treatments showed a significant improvement over the untreated control and the commercial *Ecklonia maxima* treatment for the agronomic parameters analysed, but the Qi-gen treatment was significantly the best for increasing vegetative and root biomass. Improvements were also found in plant height, leaf number and root length. The trial also revealed the significant effect on *Botrytis* control of the product Aktigen and on powdery mildew of the product Lifegen, in fact they reduced the mortality of *Valeriana officinalis* and *Raphanus sativus* seedlings.

Conclusions: A number of scientific studies have shown that the application of biofertilizers can improve plant growth, productivity, quality, and tolerance to biotic and abiotic stresses. Because of their multiple properties, they have become increasingly important as advanced agricultural techniques in global agriculture. This type of product, which includes natural substances, will contribute significantly to ecologically and economically sustainable agricultural production systems in the coming years, as well as serving as the foundation for large-scale sustainable agriculture in the future.

Keywords: Resistance inductors; Sustainable applications; Plant extract; Rhizosphere; Biofertilizers

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1. Introduction

1.1. Fertilizers: essential elements for plants and soil life

The growing demand for agricultural products to meet the demand for food for humans and animals, which has also increased in recent years for energy uses, with a steadily growing world population, cannot be met, as was the case in the recent past with the Green Revolution by exploiting genetic improvement and cultivating new land with increased use of irrigation water, simply because these are resources whose availability is limited [1-3]. Among the possible ways to maintain and if possible increase the productivity of cultivated fields, limiting ourselves to the field of mineral plant nutrition, it is reasonable to focus on:

- New types of fertilisers;
- Increasing the fertiliser unit (uf) efficiency of existing and of course new products;
- Increasing the bioavailability of certain elements already present in soils in a form not available for plant nutrition.

This means that we must aim for fertilisation that is even more targeted to the real needs of the plant and the characteristics of the soil-plant system, with fertiliser products that are able to follow the needs in relation to the different phenological phases that dictate the evolution of requirements. Increasing the efficiency of fertiliser units (NUE, Nutrient Use Efficiency) of products is not a choice, but a compulsory step to reach production objectives in terms of quantity (food security) and quality (food safety), always bearing in mind the sustainability of resources [4-7]. The strategy of increasing NUE is theoretically applicable to all fertility elements, but may find greater application in nitrogen (N) and phosphate (P) fertilisers. In this scenario, however, the technology and development of new fertilisers, especially from renewable resources, through the use of agro-industrial by-products from other production processes, must find more space [8]. The production of fertilisers from renewable resources, for example, is not only possible, but today it is necessary, as the new lines outlined in the Circular Economy issued by the European Union in 2014 also dictate [9,10]. The concept of the Circular Economy is based on the need to reuse and recycle resources, which, in this way, would remain in the economic cycle for a longer time than in the current, so-called linear model, in which resources are placed along the unidirectional line of extraction-production-consumption-disposal (*take-make-use-dispose*). In the circular economy model, on the other hand, resources are more appropriately placed in the extraction-production-consumption-reuse (*take-make-use-reuse*) type cycle [11]. Globally, it is estimated that the economic system consumes around 65 billion tonnes of raw materials per year, many of which are finite and whose extraction and processing comes at an environmental cost to the planet. In the same way, the production of fertilisers from the recovery from organic-based by-products of nutrients is theoretically possible on all fertility elements, although today the tendency is to favour nitrogen, phosphorus and certain trace elements [12].

1.2. Raw materials and environmental friendliness

In recent years, the protection of production quality and the environment has become increasingly important. On the one hand, this is the logical consequence of the end consumer's increased demand for environmentally friendly foodstuffs, on the other hand, one has to deal with the not entirely renewable resources that are used as raw materials for the production of a large part of mineral fertilisers [13]. In a broader perspective involving concepts of sustainability and recycling/recovery, organic by-products can also play a significant role, albeit a secondary role and certainly not on the assumption that self-sufficiency can be achieved with such products [14]. Products of plant and animal origin have two particularities from an economic-commercial point of view: their availability is infinite, just as their production has no geographical constraints since there can be plant and/or animal residues from which fertilisers can be obtained anywhere in the world. Organic fertilisers of plant origin, in most cases, are a source of nitrogen and, in the case of boron, also potassium; animal fertilisers often contain phosphorus and, in some cases, potassium in addition to nitrogen [15]. Considering the types of organic fertilisers most commonly used in Italy, and leaving aside plant extracts mostly used as biostimulants, usually products of plant origin have a low nutrient content while animal derivatives reach contents comparable to some mineral fertilisers [16,17].

1.3. Alternatives to conventional fertilisers

In order to decrease the depletion of resources and the degradation of the ecosystems, more sustainable management of agricultural land areas is required. It is imperative to reduce input costs, as well as reliance on chemical fertilizers and pesticides, which can pose multiple risks to human health and the environment if misused [18-24]. Farmers and researchers are therefore urged to find alternative solutions in order to increase agricultural productivity while preserving natural resources and reducing land use in particular. The use of alternative and sustainable approaches to address these issues is therefore of great interest [19,20,23,25]. The most investigated and promising products to make

agriculture more sustainable are organic products called biostimulants, which have been proposed several times. Plant-derived biostimulants (PDBs) are an efficient, eco-friendly alternative to synthetic biostimulants [20,21,25,26,27,28]. Currently, farmers and researchers are focusing on biostimulants to improve agricultural sustainability, but there are other natural products that need to be considered, studied, and assessed as well. In this review, we will discuss how plant extracts can be used to improve agricultural sustainability, particularly crop quality and production. Plant metabolites influence phenotype and physiological responses of plants [29]. The effects of plant extracts on hormones [30], organic acids [31], polyphenols [30], and sugars [31] have been reported in several previous studies. Quality traits (fruit size, colour, firmness, macro- and micronutrient contents, vitamins, polyphenols) and quantity traits (yield per square meter) are influenced by both biotic and abiotic stresses [32]. To cope with stress, crops shift from the first metabolism to the second metabolism, utilizing their energy reserves instead of concentrating on yielding. Following the recommendations of the European Union, synthetic plant protection products should be replaced by natural ones to improve agricultural sustainability in order to prevent this reduction of yield. Plant extracts have been extensively investigated as a practical approach to improving crop production sustainability, including producing biostimulants for specific crops. Plant extracts are still poorly understood even though they are often used to replace synthetic products such as fungicides, pesticides, and herbicides, despite their economic relevance. It is still largely unknown whether plant extracts can be used to overcome both biotic and abiotic stresses.

The main objective of this article is to report the results obtained from the use of innovative fertilisers with added plant extracts in agriculture. In particular, this article will deal with two important topics:

- Study of the effect of innovative fertilisers on the biomass of vegetable plants;
- Possible control on mortality due to diseases such as *Botrytis* and powdery mildew. The information reported in this research work can support the design of cultivation systems in which agricultural sustainability is fundamental due to the presence of plant extracts as an alternative to synthetic plant protection products.

Figure 1 Details of the plants used in the trial

2. Materials and methods

The plants were grown in pots under controlled conditions; 30 seedlings per thesis, divided into 3 replications of 10 plants each, were planted in early January 2024. The plants used in the trial were *Valeriana officinalis* L. (Figure 1) and *Raphanus sativus*. All plants were fertilised with a slow-release fertiliser (1 kg m⁻³ of Osmocote Pro® for 6 months) introduced into the growing medium at the time of transplanting.

The five experimental groups in cultivation were:

- Group control (CTRL): (peat 70% + pumice 20%), irrigated with water and previously fertilised substrate;
- Group with Aktigen (AT): (peat 70% + pumice 20%), irrigated with water and previously fertilised substrate, (3 ml per plant once a week); Aktigen is a formulation based on boron (2%) ethanolamine + plant

extracts. It prevents boron deficiency; facilitates the transport of sugars across membranes; stimulates the growth of apical meristems; stimulates pollen tube elongation; regulates cell multiplication; promotes fructification and increased resistance to physiopathologies;

- Group with Lifegen (LI): (peat 70% + pumice 20%), irrigated with water and previously fertilised substrate, (3 ml per plant once a week); Lifegen is a fertiliser based on zinc (2%) + plant extracts; promotes chlorophyll formation and stabilises ribosomes; improves cell relaxation; increases fruit production and colouration; prevents fruit drop;
- Group with Qi-gen (QI): (peat 70% + pumice 20%), irrigated with water and previously fertilised substrate, (3 ml per plant once a week); Qi-gen is a fertiliser based on iron (EDTA) (2%) + plant extracts. It reactivates root growth; promotes root uptake; stimulates the plant to thicken root cortical tissue.
- Group with *Ecklonia maxima* (EK): (peat 70% + pumice 20%), irrigated with water and previously fertilised substrate, (3 ml per plant once a week).

The plants were watered once a day and cultivated for 5 months. The plants were drip-irrigated. Irrigation was activated by a timer whose schedule was adjusted weekly according to weather conditions and leaching fraction. On 5 May 2024, plant height, number of leaves, primary root length (mm), biomass of the aerial and root system, and number of dead plants (*Botrytis* and powdery mildew) were recorded.

2.1. Statistics

The experiment was carried out in a randomized complete block design. Collected data were analysed by one-way ANOVA, using GLM univariate procedure, to assess significant ($P \leq 0.05$, 0.01 and 0.001) differences among treatments. Mean values were then separated by LSD multiple-range test ($P = 0.05$). Statistics and graphics were supported by the programs Costat (version 6.451) and Excel (Office 2010).

3. Results and Discussion

The experiment showed that the use of innovative fertilisers enriched with plant extracts can indeed significantly improve the vegetative and root growth of *Valeriana officinalis* L. and *Raphanus sativus* (**Table 1** and **Table 2**). All treatments showed a significant improvement over the untreated control and the commercial *Ecklonia maxima* treatment for the agronomic parameters analysed, but the Qi-gen treatment was significantly the best for increasing vegetative and root biomass (**Figure 4** and **Figure 5**).

Improvements were also found in plant height, leaf number and root length. The trial also revealed the significant effect on *Botrytis* control of the product Aktigen and on powdery mildew of the product Lifegen, in fact they reduced the mortality of *Valeriana officinalis* and *Raphanus sativus* seedlings (Figures 2, Figures 3 and Figures 6).

A plant-derived biostimulant improves plant growth, quality, photosynthesis, tolerance to both biotic and abiotic stresses, as well as efficiency in using resources (nutrients, fertilizers, and water) by modulating plant biochemical, molecular, and physiological processes [18,26]. Understanding the mechanism of action of biostimulants is crucial to improving their effectiveness and optimizing industrial processes. In addition to being rich in bioactive compounds, these bio-products are easily absorbed by plants at low dosages [22,24,27]. It is important to note that the effects of PDBs depend on the crop species, cultivar, development stage, environmental conditions, as well as the dose, time, and application method [22,24]. In response to consumer expectations for healthy food, European agricultural and food safety policies encourage more environmentally friendly and safe agricultural practices [18,22]. In order to produce potential biostimulants, moringa (*Moringa oleifera*) is one of the most commonly used higher plants. Many crops have been tested for its impact, including cherry tomatoes [33], coriander [34], plum trees [35], wheat [36], pea plants [37], and rocket [38]. Research confirmed the positive effects of their use, observing an increase in yields, the content of photosynthetic pigments, oils, elements, proteins, total sugars, phenols, ascorbic acid, anthocyanins, growth-promoting hormones, and antioxidant activity. For the production of biostimulants of plant growth, vegetables are often used as raw materials. In Pretorius (2007) [39], seeds of *Lupinus albus* were studied and found to be biostimulatory for coleoptile and root growth, both in the field and in the glasshouse. Furthermore, the author studied the effects of combing extracts from *Lupinus albus* seeds with extracts of seeds or plant parts from the Pink family and Alfalfa species. This suggests that synergism is involved in the biological processes involved, as the extracts or preparations of the single species have a higher biostimulatory efficacy. Licorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*) is the second most commonly used raw material. As a result of its application (improved growth, development, and chemical composition), common bean [40], onion [41], almond [42], and fennel [43] were found to benefit. Additionally, foliar spraying with garlic extracts (*Allium sativum*) was shown to increase yields and quality in the cultivation of faba beans [44], eggplant (improved growth and development, antioxidant enzymes, photosynthesis) [45], and snap beans (enhanced growth, leaf and pod chemical

compositions) [46]. The biological properties of aromatic plants and medicinal plants rich in essential oils include biostimulant properties [47]. In particular, rosemary [47,48], eucalyptus [48], thyme [49,50] and tansy [50] are the most popular herbs. Among the essential oils extracted from rosemary and eucalyptus are 1,8-cineole, which has antibacterial, antifungal, herbicidal, and insecticidal properties [48]. Plant organs, genetics, growth conditions, soil composition, harvest stage, and microorganism colonization of roots may affect oil composition [51,52,53,54]. Abiotic stress tolerance is essential for both crop productivity and environmental sustainability (less water and fertilizer usage) [55]. Even though significant progress has been made in genetic transformation over the last few years, abiotic stress tolerance remains one of the most difficult problems to solve [56]. Plants performing better under terminal heat and drought stress include accumulating compatible solutes, reducing stomatal conductance, and activating antioxidant systems [57]. In order to combat the adverse impact of abiotic stress, a variety of strategies are used, including choosing the right cultivar, growing period, sowing density, water, and fertilizer, as well as controlling temperature, radiation, and atmospheric conditions. Bulgari et al. [58] also recommend soilless cultivation, grafting, and genetic improvement. Furthermore, exogenous application of osmoprotectants, stress signaling molecules, and plant extracts can be considered as a means of improving the aforementioned mechanisms. The use of plant extracts appears, however, to be the most eco-friendly and cheapest option [57,59]. In this research paper, the application of innovative fertilisers with added plant extracts resulted in a significant improvement in plant growth and increased protection against pathogens such as botrytis and powdery mildew, confirming results obtained in other research by other authors.

Table 1 Evaluation of innovative fertilisers on agronomic characters on plants of *Valeriana officinalis* L.

<i>Valeriana officinalis</i> L.	PH (cm)	LN (n°)	VW (g)	RW (g)	RL (cm)
CTRL	6.26 d	8.00 d	16.24 e	12.33 d	3.75 d
AT	8.25 b	11.80 b	18.36 c	14.42 b	5.33 b
LI	8.31 b	11.83 b	18.57 b	14.68 b	5.36 b
QI	10.27 a	14.60 a	20.36 a	15.62 a	6.54 a
EK	7.37 c	9.44 c	17.39 d	13.51 c	4.63 c
ANOVA	***	***	***	***	***

One-way ANOVA; n.s. – non significant; *, **, *** – significant at $P \leq 0.05$, 0.01 and 0.001, respectively; different letters for the same element indicate significant differences according to Tukey's (HSD) multiple-range test ($P = 0.05$).

Parameters: PH = plant height (cm); LN = leaves number (cm); TLA = total leaves area (mm²); VW = vegetative weight (g); RW = roots weight (g); RL = roots length (cm). Treatments: CTRL=control; AT= Aktigen; LI= Lifegen; QI= Qi-gen; EK= *Ecklonia maxima*.

Table 2 Evaluation of innovative fertilisers on agronomic characters on plants of *Raphanus sativus*

<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	PH (cm)	LN (n°)	VW (g)	RW (g)	RL (cm)
CTRL	8.38 e	7.23 d	17.39 d	12.26 d	3.27 d
AT	10.46 c	9.23 c	19.36 b	14.72 b	5.23 b
LI	10.77 b	11.64 b	19.34 b	14.84 b	5.22 b
QI	12.75 a	14.81 a	20.87 a	15.52 a	6.36 a
EK	9.37 d	7.84 d	18.35 c	13.59 c	4.38 c
ANOVA	***	***	***	***	***

One-way ANOVA; n.s. – non significant; *, **, *** – significant at $P \leq 0.05$, 0.01 and 0.001, respectively; different letters for the same element indicate significant differences according to Tukey's (HSD) multiple-range test ($P = 0.05$).

Parameters: PH = plant height (cm); LN = leaves number (cm); TLA = total leaves area (mm²); VW = vegetative weight (g); RW = roots weight (g); RL = roots length (cm). Treatments: CTRL=control; AT= Aktigen; LI= Lifegen; QI= Qi-gen; EK= *Ecklonia maxima*.

Legend: QI: Qi-gen; LI: Lifegen; AT: Aktigen; EK: *Ecklonia maxima*; CT: control

Figure 2 Effect of innovative fertilisers with added plant extracts on the control of *Botrytis cinerea* and Powdery mildew in *Valeriana officinalis* L.

Legend: QI: Qi-gen; LI: Lifegen; AT: Aktigen; EK: *Ecklonia maxima*; CT: control

Figure 3 Effect of innovative fertilisers with added plant extracts on the control of *Botrytis cinerea* and Powdery mildew in *Raphanus sativus*

Figure 4 Effect of innovative fertilisers on vegetative biomass of *Valeriana officinalis* L. compared with fertilised control. Legend: QI: Qi-gen; LI: Lifegen; AT: Aktigen; EK: *Ecklonia maxima*; CT: control

Figure 5 Effect of Qi-gen (QI) on vegetative and radical biomass of *Valeriana officinalis* L. compared with fertilised control (CT)

Figure 6 Effect of Aktigen (AT) on *Botrytis* control compared to untreated control (CT)

4. Conclusion

Increasing the production of high quality food for an ever-growing global population is one of the most important objectives of modern agriculture: reducing environmental impact and increasing food production. As part of this research, we examined whether fertilisers with plant extracts would be able to support both of these objectives. A number of scientific studies have shown that the application of these products can improve plant growth, productivity, quality, and tolerance to biotic and abiotic stresses. Because of their multiple properties, they have become increasingly important as advanced agricultural techniques in global agriculture. This type of product, which includes natural substances, will contribute significantly to ecologically and economically sustainable agricultural production systems in the coming years, as well as serving as the foundation for large-scale sustainable agriculture in the future.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The research is part of the 'PROVAMIC' project: Production and evaluation of microbic strains on plants vegetable and ornamental plants. I would like to thank the company Agrogen for their collaboration, in particular in the person of Dr. Giordano Menci, who actively collaborated in the Provamic project.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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